

**PROFICIENCY TEST
FOR INTESTINAL DIAGNOSIS OF
ECHINOCOCCUS MULTILOCULARIS
IN FOXES USING SSCT**

FINAL REPORT

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1. INTRODUCTION

A proficiency test (PT) dedicated to intestinal diagnosis of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in foxes was organized by the Anses Rabies and wildlife laboratory. The objective was to assess the technical performance of laboratories based on the Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT, Umhang et al. 2011). This work was undertaken in the frame of task 3 from work package 4 of the One Health European Joint Project (OHEJP) MEME (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/jrp-meme/>).

The aim of the PT is to evaluate for the first time the ability of participants to realize intestinal diagnosis of *E. multilocularis* in foxes from intestines samples by removing the worms from the intestinal mucosa and realize morphological identification.

2. GENERAL INFORMATION

2.1 IDENTIFICATION OF COORDINATORS AND STAFF INVOLVED IN THE STUDY

The laboratory organizing the PT SSCT is the Anses (France) which has described the technique.

Coordinators:

- G. Umhang (Head of French NRL *Echinococcus* spp.)
- F. Boué (Head of Wildlife Surveillance and Eco-epidemiology Unit)

Technical Staff:

- F. Bastien (Technician of Wildlife Surveillance and Eco-epidemiology Unit)
- C. Caillot (Technician of Wildlife Surveillance and Eco-epidemiology Unit)

2.2 INSTRUCTION TO PARTICIPANTS

The call for participation in the PT SSCT was sent to laboratories by e-mail in June 2021. A panel of five coded samples to be tested was sent to participating laboratories by a specialized carrier. Each sample corresponds to a frozen half-segment of small intestines of red fox obtain after a longitudinal cut and was susceptible to be infected by *E. multilocularis* but also by others intestinal parasites. All the intestines samples were previously decontaminated by a storage of one week at -80°C to prevent any risk of infection. The shipment of the panel to the laboratories was achieved on October 25th 2021 at -20°C temperature by an international agreed carrier and under UN3373 conditions to avoid exposure hazards. All the panels were received frozen by the participating laboratories with a time range of one to four days. It was recommended to laboratories to store the panel at -20°C as soon as received.

Laboratories were invited to test the samples with the SSCT as detailed in the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) provided. The expected results were a binomial response “positive” or “negative” regarding the presence of *E. multilocularis* worms for each samples, completed by the worm burden observed in case of positive samples. Instruction to participants was sent in the same time than the sending of the samples in October. The deadline for result reception was fixed on November 26th 2021.

3. PROFICIENCY TEST ITEMS

3.1 PREPARATION OF THE PROFICIENCY TEST ITEMS

The positive half-segments used in this PT were obtained from French or Polish regions highly endemic for *E. multilocularis*. After dividing the small intestine in four equal segments (the fifth segment is

considered to be the large intestine), half of a segment obtained after a longitudinal cut was analyzed using SSCT to estimate the worm burden. The other half of the segment was used for the PT.

A proof of concept was previously realized at the Anses to assure that *E. multilocularis* worms will be in the half-segments selected for positive samples into the panels even if only the other half from the same segment has been analyzed. In all, 30 positive intestines of red foxes were analyzed to provide results for one to four couple of half-segments corresponding to segments S1 to S4 finally representing 158 exploitable half-segments. In the 19 half-segment negative for one half-segment but positive for the other one, a maximum burden of six *E. multilocularis* worms (average 2.2 worms) were identified in the positive one (Table 1).

Table 1: *E. multilocularis* worm burden of the 8 half-segments from each of the 30 foxes intestines used for both the proof of concept and the proficiency test. An asterisk indicated worm burden for segments analyzed entirely (not for the two half). Red cells indicated when a different qualitative result (positive/negative) was obtained for a couple of half-segments. Worm burden is in red when it is more than the double for one half-segment in the couple. PT referred to half segments used for the PT.

Origin	Fox ID	Total	Worm burden							
			S1		S2		S3		S4	
			S1.1	S1.2	S2.1	S2.2	S3.1	S3.2	S4.1	S4.2
France	ATT	390	5	10	75	55	50	105	45	45
France	21073	30	5*		10	5	5	0	5*	
France	21102	80	25*		20	10	10	5	10*	
France	9877	21	0	0	0	1	7	10	0	3
France	9875	609	2	1	2	0	131	234	89	150
France	STX1	21	1	3	2	3	2	4	3	3
France	STX2	30	0	0	0	0	15	9	0	6
France	STX3	2423	2	1	22	27	51	84	707	1529
France	21761	370	4	5	24	PT	111	PT	52	39
France	21760	26	7	8	0	0	0	0	8	3
France	21762	48	2	8	8	8	3	7	10	2
France	21752	128	1	2	3	4	36	PT	23	PT
France	21753	134	0	1	0	3	22	PT	43	PT
France	21755	271	2	3	5	1	31	PT	99	PT
France	21751	494	2	1	3	6	18	PT	223	PT
France	21744	248	2	0	5	6	1	0	117	PT
France	21746	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
France	21742	97	0	2	0	1	1	7	43	PT
France	21738	1202	84	PT	109	PT	207	PT	201	PT
Poland	21932	13	0	0	0*		0*		10	3
Poland	21935	368	0	2	79	PT	72	PT	32	PT
Poland	21933	6205	1857	/	2410*		80*		1	0
Poland	21937	72	2	8	28		24		4	6
Poland	21920	319	1	1	21*		67	PT	81	PT
Poland	21930	42061	162	PT	1960	2079	6698	5040	10395	15565
Poland	21922	6	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0
Poland	21921	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Poland	21924	829	2	7	27	PT	146	PT	237	PT
Poland	21927	74	1	4	56*		9		0	4
Poland	21929	180	25	PT	61	PT	0	0	7	1

For isolation of positive half-segment, a threshold of a minimum worm burden of 15 was established. Finally, the positive samples of the panel were constituted of two blindly coded positive half-segments with estimation of the worm burden ranging from 18 to 237 according to the other half-segment (Table 1).

Negative segments were obtained from a south-west French region (Landes) free of *E. multilocularis*. A fecal sample of each fox was also tested by corpo-qPCR to confirm the absence of infection. Three blindly coded negative half-segments were added to the two positive in the panel of each participant.

The presence of other worms in positive and negative half-segments was possible and not removed to reproduce as much as possible standard conditions of a diagnosis process. Stability of the panel samples for SSCT was evaluated after a frozen step as realized for the preparation of the panel and was validated at Anses.

3.2 IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROFICIENCY TEST ITEMS

For each panel, all items were coded randomly. The code was constituted by a random number ranging between 1 to 270 corresponding to all the 28 positive and 242 negative half-segments available at the Anses.

3.3 REGISTERED PARTICIPATING LABORATORIES

Fourteen laboratories registered in the SSCT proficiency test. Registered laboratories included 12 laboratories from the EJPOH Meme and two invited laboratories from European Union (EU). The geographical origin of registered laboratories is presented in Figure 2. The participants are listed here by alphabetical order:

- Anses (France); organizer
- BIOR (Latvia)
- CVRL (Ireland)
- FFA (Finland), invited
- FLI (Germany)
- INIAV (Portugal)
- ISS (Italy)
- PIWET (Poland)
- SSI (Denmark)
- SVA (Sweden)
- UT (Estonia)
- VEINST (Croatia), invited
- VETINST (Norway)
- VFL (Estonia)

Figure 1: Geographical origin of the registered laboratories for the SSCT PT.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Results of participating laboratories

All the 14 laboratories sent back their results in due time. Globally, two of 14 (14%) of the laboratories (21-3 and 21-13) provided discrepant results. In both cases only one of the five samples was concerned corresponding in one case to one false positive and one false negative in the other case.

The false positive diagnosis from laboratory 21-3 was established on the observation of one scolex and one free gravid proglottid. In addition to the free endemic status of the region of origin and the negative corpo-qPCR diagnostic of negative samples, the analysis of all the seven others half-segments from the concerned intestine was analyzed by SSCT and confirmed to be negative.

Regarding the false negative from laboratory 21-13, a worm burden of 24 worms was observed in the other half. According to the participant, only one fragment ascribable to a gravid proglottid *Echinococcus*-like was observed and then considered as an accidental detection to diagnostic the sample as negative.

4.2. Analysis of the estimated worm burden

According to the threshold of a minimum of 15 worms observed in the first half-segment and the worm burden estimated by the organizers in the panel of positive half-segments, three categories of worm burden were decided: low (18 to 43 worms; 12 couples), moderate (61-117 worms; 10 couples), high (146-237 worms; 6 couples). The repartition of the positive half-segments was realized in order to have a high difference of worm burden between the two positive half-segments (low and moderate or moderate and high or low and high) for each participant.

When analyzing both half-segments of the intestines, similar worm burden was expected even if in some cases a larger difference with more than the double of the worms may be observed. Nevertheless, it is impossible to predict the exact worm burden of the second half-segment using the one obtained from the first one, preventing any evaluation of the participant about a correct worm burden estimation. One could consider also that there will be theoretically no reason to have globally more worms in the first half analyzed by the organizers versus the second half distributed to the participants.

Table 2: Worm burden observed in the half-segments by the organizer and the participants.

Laboratory ID	ID PT	Worm burden		ID PT	Worm burden	
		Organizer	Participants		Organizer	Participants
21-01	108	22	60	100	79	1
21-02	251	23	5	128	81	23
21-03	23	25	16	69	109	20
21-04	30	43	15	98	201	25
21-05	9	24	8	230	84	33
21-06	227	61	38	169	223	244
21-07	224	32	54	197	146	81
21-08	110	36	40	17	162	250
21-09	210	27	31	103	111	27
21-10	25	43	17	129	207	51
21-11	74	18	29	183	72	43
21-12	63	67	34	151	237	219
21-13	208	24	0	195	99	60
21-14	48	31	21	96	117	2

On the 13 couples of half-segments with a minimum of 15 worms used for the proof of concept, more than the double of worms was observed for only two couples (14%) originating from two different foxes (Table 1). According to the results of the PT, this situation occurred for half of the 28 couples used. Among this 14 cases, more than the double of worms were observed by the participants in three cases, when it was obtained by the organizers in 11 cases. Globally, higher worm burden were obtained by the organizers. It was mainly observed for moderate worm burden with a systematically lower estimation when it was more equilibrated for low and high worm burden (Table 2).

5. OVERALL DIAGNOSIS CONCLUSION

Fourteen laboratories provided answers to the PT SSCT organized in the context of the EJPOH MEME project. Only two laboratories (14% of laboratories) provided a discordant result. For each laboratory, only one sample was concerned. These results can still be considered as very encouraging as any laboratory realized SSCT in routine diagnostic intestinal analysis (excepting organizer Anses). The long routine experience of the organizers with SSCT may explained also the globally higher worm burden they observed.

Furthermore, most of the participants have chosen to use a corpo-PCR approach for definitive host diagnostic if performed rather as an intestinal morphological techniques (SSCT, SCT, IST, ...) requiring to set up the method specifically and only for this PT.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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